

State Estimation for Vehicle Charging IoT-Enabled CPS Nexus using AMQP and EKF

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Abstract—Designing the real-time cyber twin ecosystem considering EV charging stations, smart grids, water distribution systems, and IoT networks are challenging tasks. This paper presents a comprehensive state-space model for an Industrial Cyber-Physical System (CPS) Nexus integrating EV charging stations, smart grids, water distribution systems, and IoT networks. This subsystem each communicate with other through AMQP (Advanced Message Queuing Protocol). For this big system, some of the states are unobservable, therefore we develop an extended Kalman Filter framework for state estimation and demonstrate its performance through numerical simulations. In future, we will consider the cyber attack and apply the controller to regulate the CPS states.

Index Terms—Electric Vehicles Extended Kalman filter HAAC system Smart Grids Water System

I. INTRODUCTION

Developing the real-time twin ecosystem considering EV charging stations, smart grids, water distribution systems, and IoT networks are challenging tasks. Motivation by this, this framework presents a comprehensive state-space model for an Industrial Cyber-Physical System (CPS) Nexus incorporating EV charging stations, smart grids, water distribution systems, and IoT networks. This subsystem can communicate with other through AMQP (Advanced Message Queuing Protocol). In this CPS, some of the states are unobservable, therefore we develop an extended Kalman Filter algorithm for state estimation and demonstrate its performance through numerical simulations.

There are some existing works that focus the CPS digital state estimations [1], [2], [3], [4]. To begin with, the particle filtering (PF) method is employed for nonlinear systems state estimation in [5]. The PF is computationally expensive, suffer from particle degeneracy, and require frequent resampling [6]. The least mean squared and least squared approaches for power system have adopted to predict the CPS state estimation [7]. The machine learning based state estimation framework has been proposed in [8],

In summary, the modeling the whole system incorporating all real-time daily used subsystem are changing tasks as shown in Fig. 1. In this paper, we develop an Extended Kalman filter framework for state estimation and demonstrate its performance through numerical simulations.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: Section II describes the real-time interconnected system, including electric vehicles, smart grids, water, and HVAC. Section III demonstrates the EKF, followed by simulation results and conclusions in Section V.

II. REAL-TIME INTERCONNECTED SYSTEM INCLUDING ELECTRICAL VEHICLE, SMART GRID, WATER AND HAAC

In real-time, there are interconnected ecosystem such as electric vehicle (EV) battery charging dynamics, smart grid infrastructure, water systems, and HVAC subsystems. Inspired

Fig. 1: Proposed interconnected real-time systems.

my [9], [10], [11], [12], [13], [14], [15] this paper models a real time cyber-physical nexus ecosystem integrating electric vehicle (EV) battery charging dynamics, smart grid infrastructure,

water systems, and HVAC subsystems. The system (physical and sensing) is modeled in discrete-time state-space form:

$$\mathbf{x}_{t+1} = f(\mathbf{x}_t, \mathbf{u}_t) + \mathbf{w}_t. \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{z}_t = h(\mathbf{x}_t) + \mathbf{v}_t.$$

Here, $\mathbf{x}_t \in \mathbb{R}^{13} = [SOC, P, T_{batt}, V_d, Freq, SOC_{bess}, W_{level}, Flow, Pump_{eff}, Temp_{zone}, HVAC, Latency, PacketLoss]^T$ is the state vector, $\mathbf{u}_t \in \mathbb{R}^6 = [u_0, u_1, u_2, u_3, u_4, u_5]^T$ is the control input, $\mathbf{z}_t \in \mathbb{R}^5$ is the measurement vector and \mathbf{w}_t , and \mathbf{v}_t are the Gaussian distributed process and measurement noise. The physical system without process noise is:

$$\mathbf{x}_{t+1} = f(\mathbf{x}_t, \mathbf{u}_t)$$

$$= \mathbf{x}_t + \Delta t \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \frac{P_t}{Q_{batt}} - k_{deg} T_{batt} \\ u_0 - R_{chg} P_t \\ \frac{P_t^2}{0.1} + 25 \\ \frac{1}{C_g} (SOC_{bess} - (P + T_{batt})) \\ \frac{1}{2H} (u_1 - D \cdot Freq) \\ u_2 \\ \frac{1}{A_{tank}} (Flow + Pump_{eff}) \\ \frac{g}{L_{pipe}} (W_{level} - f_{ric} |Flow|) \\ \frac{(u_3 - Pump_{eff})}{2} \\ \frac{1}{C_{th}} (HVAC - U (Temp_{zone} - 25)) \\ \frac{(u_4 - HVAC)}{5} \\ \frac{1}{\tau_{net}} (u_5 - Latency) \\ 0 \quad (\text{PacketLoss updated separately}) \end{bmatrix}$$

State Descriptions:

- 1) SOC : State of Charge of the EV battery [%]
- 2) P : Power demand by the vehicle [kW]
- 3) T_{batt} : Temperature of the EV battery [$^{\circ}C$]
- 4) V_d : Grid voltage [V]
- 5) $Freq$: Frequency of the power grid [Hz]
- 6) SOC_{bess} : SOC of the Battery Energy Storage System [%]
- 7) W_{level} : Water tank level [m]
- 8) $Flow$: Water flow rate [m^3/s]
- 9) $Pump_{eff}$: Pump efficiency [-]
- 10) $Temp_{zone}$: HVAC-controlled zone temperature [$^{\circ}C$]
- 11) $HVAC$: HVAC power [kW]
- 12) $Latency$: Network latency [ms]
- 13) $PacketLoss$: Network packet loss [%]

Control Descriptions:

- 1) u_0 : EV power control input
- 2) u_1 : Grid frequency regulation control
- 3) u_2 : BESS charging/discharging
- 4) u_3 : Pump control
- 5) u_4 : HVAC control input
- 6) u_5 : Network latency control

The packet loss is

$$PacketLoss = \alpha(1 - e^{-\beta \cdot Latency})$$

Here, α is the packet loss coefficient and β is the packet loss decay rate. It can be seen that there are some states such as $P, T_{batt}, Freq, SOC_{bess}, W_{level}, Pump_{eff}, Temp_{zone}, PacketLoss$ are unobservable by sensors and therefore, they

will need to estimate to properly monitor the systems. We will adopt the EKF for these state estimations.

III. EKF ALGORITHM FOR STATE OBSERVABLE

There are two steps for the EKF process as demonstrated in fig. 2 [16] [17]. To begin with, the algorithm will predict the state and error covariance. On the correction step, it will compute the gain, update state estimation and error covariance. In future, we will consider the cyber attack on the communication networks and will use the UKF [17].

Fig. 2: EKF Algorithm for real-time nexus state estimation and future work.

IV. NUMERICAL SIMULATION RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The simulation are parameters are described in Table I. In future, we will tune the parameters. The discreet time step size is 0.1 second. The simulation is conducted using python based Colab.

Fig. 3: True and estimated states.

TABLE I: Simulation Parameters for the Nexus System

System Parameter	Symbol	Value
Battery capacity	Q_{batt}	100.0
Battery degradation rate	k_{deg}	1×10^{-5}
Charging resistance	R_{chg}	0.1
Grid capacitance	C_g	0.5
Grid inertia	H	5.0
Frequency damping	D	0.1
Tank area	A_{tank}	10.0
Gravity	g	9.81
Pipe length	L_{pipe}	100.0
Friction coefficient	f_{ric}	0.02
Thermal capacitance	C_{th}	0.8
Heat loss coefficient	U	0.2
Network latency constant	τ_{net}	0.1
Packet loss coefficient	α	0.5
Packet loss decay rate	β	0.1

The simulation results are demonstrated in Figs. 3-5.

The algorithm can able to predict all states with high accuracies. The gain is computed in an optional way so the true and estimated are accurately reflected over time.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This paper present the EKF based state estimation for real-time CPS state estimation. Extensive simulation shows that the the algorithm can predicted all states with high accuracy. In future, we will consider the cyber attack and do the extensive simulation. We will try to apply the controller to regulate the CPS states.

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Fig. 4: True and estimated states over time

Fig. 5: MSE

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